

Why are ceremonies and Rituals important?

Luke 2:21-40

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Luke 2:21 And when eight days had passed, before His circumcision, His name was *then* called Jesus, the name given by the angel before He was conceived in the womb.

Luke 2:22 And when the days for their purification according to the law of Moses were completed, they brought Him up to Jerusalem to present Him to the Lord **23** (as it is written in the Law of the Lord, “EVERY *firstborn* MALE THAT OPENS THE WOMB SHALL BE CALLED HOLY TO THE LORD”), **24** and to offer a sacrifice according to what was said in the Law of the Lord, “A PAIR OF TURTLEDOVES OR TWO YOUNG PIGEONS.”

Luke 2:25 And there was a man in Jerusalem whose name was Simeon; and this man was righteous and devout, looking for the consolation of Israel; and the Holy Spirit was upon him. **26** And it had been revealed to him by the Holy Spirit that he would not see death before he had seen the Lord’s Christ. **27** And he came in the Spirit into the temple; and when the parents brought in the child Jesus, ^{1^a}to carry out for Him the custom of the Law, **28** then he took Him into his arms, and blessed God, and said,
29 “Now Lord, You are releasing Your bond-servant to depart in peace,
According to Your word;
30 For my eyes have seen Your salvation,
31 Which You have prepared in the presence of all peoples,
32 A LIGHT OF REVELATION TO THE GENTILES,
And the glory of Your people Israel.”

Luke 2:33 And His father and mother were amazed at the things which were being said about Him. **34** And Simeon blessed them and said to Mary His mother, “Behold, this *Child* is appointed for the fall and rise of many in Israel, and for a sign to be opposed — **35** and a sword will pierce even your own soul — to the end that thoughts from many hearts may be revealed.”

Luke 2:36 And there was a prophetess, Anna the daughter of Phanuel, of the tribe of Asher. She was advanced in years and had lived with *her* husband seven years after her marriage, **37** and then as a widow to the age of eighty-four. She never left the temple, serving night and day with fastings and prayers. **38** At that very moment she came up and *began* giving thanks to God, and continued to speak of Him to all those who were looking for the redemption of Jerusalem.

Luke 2:39 When they had performed everything according to the Law of the Lord, they returned to Galilee, to their own city of Nazareth. **40** The Child continued to grow and become strong, ¹increasing in wisdom; and the grace of God was upon Him.

If you sit back and think for a moment, how many ceremonies or rituals have you gone through in your life? My guess is most of us have gone through high school graduation. It is a ceremony to mark the end of our public education and it gives us credentials for when we go out and find a job. It is important for people to be educated so that they can function in society. Getting a high school degree tells employers that one is prepared to do a certain level of tasks.

Some of us have college degrees while other people have college and graduate level degrees. Each degree tells us of a level of education. Today there are all kinds of certifications one can get that would help an employer determine whether a candidate is fit for a job that they must fill. Therefore, it becomes important to have these different degrees. Each of these degrees and certifications usually comes with some kind of ceremony to mark the achievement.

We also attend wedding ceremonies where two people are joined. The ceremony marks the beginning of their lives together. During the period before the Roman Empire, the wedding ceremony was exclusively a religious event. In the Roman world, women could inherit property and thus they had to have proof that they were married so that they could inherit their husband's property. This is when the idea of a marriage license first developed. Today, the marriage license is used in the same way to determine the ownership of property. It is a necessary component of today's society.

Religions have their own ceremonies and rituals. Rituals are important because they link people together into one faith. In Luke chapter 2, we learn about a couple of rituals that Jesus and Mary had to go through, which proves to us that Jesus was Jewish. I know this should not be a shock to people, but I have seen church people become shocked to learn that Jesus was Jewish. Jesus was not a Christian. The idea of Christianity came later.

The people who followed the ways and actions of Jesus became known as Christians. This word came from the Greek word for the Messiah, Christos, and it is believed to have originated in Syria. So, Jesus was not a Christian however, his followers became Christians. Let me give you another example or two. Martin Luther was not a Lutheran. The people who followed Luther's interpretation of the Scripture and his doctrine became known as Lutherans. So, if you say you are a Lutheran, then you should follow the ways of Martin Luther. The same could be said for Methodists. John Wesley was not a Methodist. His followers are called Methodists.

Even if you are in an independent church, you are following the ways of some theologian determining what he or she thought Jesus' actions and words meant. There are many accepted interpretations of the components of Christianity. For example, should an infant be baptized? For Catholics and Orthodox followers of Jesus, the answer is yes. But that has not something that Jesus said. It was a theologian named Augustine who determined that children needed to be baptized because he believed they were created and born in sin. This is the concept of original sin. This is not something that Jesus discussed, but something that Augustine determined, and it became a tradition of the church for over 1600 years.

I am not saying that you should not have your infant baptized. It is something that you must determine for your child. It is the same as determining whether you go to a mainline denominational church, like the Lutheran Church or the Episcopal Church. There are over 1000 denominations of Christianity in the world today. Is anyone of them 100% correct about everything? Logic says that is not possible, but that has not what's important, is it? What is important is that does the domination or independent church you are a part of fulfilling your spiritual connection to Jesus.

That might sound a little strange, that there may be more than one way to worship and follow Jesus. However, with over 1000 denominations in the world, Jesus is okay with several expressions of Christianity. It would be incorrect to call some good and some bad. Again, it is up to you to learn what the theology and the doctrine are of the church that you belong to or you are thinking of belonging to and see if it fits with what you believe is correct.

I strongly believe that it is not up to me to tell people what to believe. However, it is up to me to explain the different aspects of doctrine that have been developed over the years. I have met various pastors in my days who do not agree with me on this. I taught it doctrine and theology class at a church I was appointed to. I explained to the class that I gave them the various aspects of the mainline interpretation for different doctrine and then it was up to them to decide which one they believed in. One day, while discussing the Trinity, an older gentleman got extremely angry at me and demanded I tell him which interpretation of Trinity that he was supposed to follow. I reminded him that is not my place to tell him what to think but to show him what the ideas were of the various mainline denominations and that he needed to make that choice. He became so angry that he stormed out of the classroom, never to return.

If you are watching this video or listening to the podcast, understand that is not my place to tell you what to believe. It is my place to present the possibilities to you. It is your responsibility to determine what you believe is correct and how best you can serve Jesus Christ our Lord and Savior. If you are not sure, seek someone out who knows the theology and doctrine of more than one denomination and then determine for yourself what the best course for you to follow.

Ceremonies and rituals are important because they show what our faith is all about. People think that the rituals and ceremonies are boring, especially when they are repeated over and over. We must repeat ceremonies and rituals or else they will get lost to history. There are plenty of rituals and ceremonies that used to happen that do not happen anymore. Remember that when you are in church, and you are participating in the communion ritual that this ritual has been done for 2000 years. When you are participating, you are taking part with all those who have taken communion before you and you will be connected to all those who will take it after you. Ceremonies and rituals are important for us to continue the faith in our Lord Jesus Christ.